

PREPRINT

Leveraging Technology for Scaling Teacher Professional Development

Insights into Usage, Challenges, and
Opportunities in Rural Tanzania

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Abstract

Purpose

The article examines how technology can be leveraged to scale technology-supported teacher professional development (TPD). It explores usage, challenges, and opportunities for scaling technology-supported TPD in resource-constrained contexts.

Design/Approach/Methods

This article employs design-based implementation research and participatory methodology, involving four iterative cycles/rounds of co-design with the Tanzania Institute of Education, to investigate the design and implementation of the government-led, technology-supported Mafunzo Endelevu ya Walimu Kazini program or Teachers' Continuous Professional Development. Data were collected using teacher surveys, participatory focus group discussions, interviews, and observations of Community of Learning (CoL) sessions and classroom practices in 20 schools in Tanzania.

Findings

Teachers are using technologies, including digital platforms such as WhatsApp groups for collaborative discussions, resource sharing, and peer support, and digital CoL modules. However, teachers face operational and policy-related challenges in using technology for TPD, including lack of essential technological devices, absence of software or accommodations for teachers with disabilities, lack of guidelines for tablet maintenance and replacement, limited digital literacy, and financial constraints.

Originality/Value

The article offers practical opportunities for scaling technology-supported TPD for rural teachers in low- and middle-income countries by using offline and low-cost technologies, zero-rated TPD content, and strengthened school-level peer support systems.

Keywords

Technology-supported TPD; design-based implementation research; scaling; rural Tanzania; low- and middle-income countries

Introduction

Many education systems in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) are striving to improve teacher professional development (TPD) to address challenges faced by teachers in their classrooms. In Tanzania, many teachers in rural contexts experience limited access to formal training opportunities, becoming disconnected from professional learning networks necessary for peer support to enhance their teaching effectiveness (Hardman et al., 2011). Even further, poor living and working conditions, including unreliable electricity and limited internet connectivity, mean that teachers in such contexts sometimes struggle to participate in TPD activities (UNESCO, 2016). Limited funding for TPD poses a further barrier to teachers to travel and participate in centralized TPD programs (Komba & Mwakabenga, 2019). Addressing these challenges is critical since well-supported teachers are better equipped to support effective student learning (Luciano, 2025). In this regard, governments of LMICs are increasingly adopting technology to address aforementioned challenges compounding the delivery of TPD programs. This is the case as technology is recognized as a powerful tool for ensuring that teachers have access to TPD opportunities within and outside their school contexts. While technology-supported TPD is growing, little is known about iterative, system-driven design processes and equity-focused adaptations to enhance technology use to support TPD in LMICs.

This paper reports on the insights into usage, challenges, and possibilities of leveraging technology to scale TPD in rural Tanzania. Lessons from this work have implications for TPD providers, program designers and policymakers at all educational levels in the efforts of leveraging technology for scaling TPD in LMICs to ensure that all teachers benefit from high-quality TPD programs.

Technology-driven reforms in TPD in Tanzania

A review of studies in LMICs highlights that many education systems are increasingly adopting digital technologies to enhance TPD (Hennessy et al., 2022). In Tanzania, the use of technology for TPD has evolved significantly since the 1970s, transitioning from radio and print-based programs to modern technologies (Dachi, 2016). Early initiatives relied on radio broadcasts and printed learning materials to reach teachers, particularly those in rural contexts. However, such initiatives were limited by challenges related to communication and logistics (Komba & Mwakabenga, 2019). The 2000s introduced computer labs and multimedia

resources in teacher colleges, although access was only possible for teachers in urban contexts (Swarts & Wachira, 2010). The 2010s saw a mobile revolution, with SMS-based platforms and projects such as BridgeIT enabling scalable TPD in rural areas (Trucano, 2016). By the 2020s, smartphones and televisions started to be used for TPD. However, the efforts faced challenges including unreliable infrastructure, limited digital skills among teachers, and funding constraints (UNESCO, 2018; World Bank, 2020). Despite such challenges, the historical progression reveals technology's growing role in overcoming TPD barriers, with lessons for scaling equitable education in Tanzania (Hardman et al., 2011).

In 2022, the Government of Tanzania introduced MEWAKA (Mafunzo Endelevu ya Walimu Kazini, or Teachers' Continuous Professional Development (TCPD) program nationwide. The program is decentralised, government-led, and technology-supported, with school-based teacher learning centred on semi-structured weekly CoL sessions. A key aspect of the program is its integrated technology component, designed to support CoLs but also ensure that teachers can access professional development anytime and anywhere. The component features an online Learning Management System (LMS) to provide schools with the CoL and self-study digital modules along with guidelines to support TPD. Furthermore, the tablets used for the 2022 Population and Housing Census were repurposed by the government and distributed to all primary school teachers, thus ensuring that teachers, in principle, have a device with which to access online materials. MEWAKA's design choices, such as its use of repurposed devices and a technology-led approach in schools, respond to Tanzania's educational challenges, including limited resources and limited access to digital tools. These choices were tested iteratively in our study.

Theoretical and Empirical Background

Technology use for TPD in LMICs

Many LMICs strive to integrate technology into TPD programs to improve the quality of teaching. Mobile phones and tablets have become most common tools for TPD in LMICs, especially for sharing training content, facilitating SMS-based learning communities, and providing and receiving feedback (West & Vosloo, 2013). Again, mobile learning has been found to enable teachers in these contexts to access TPD materials that they can use without the need for sophisticated technological infrastructure (UNESCO, 2016). Radio and television broadcasts have also become useful, especially during periods of school closures, as seen during the COVID-19

pandemic. In connected regions, LMS and open educational resources platforms have allowed for more sustained and self-paced TPD (Hennessy et al., 2022).

The technology-supported TPD ecosystem framework (Figure 2) developed by Hennessy et al. (2022) shows that the use of technology for TPD in LMICs brings challenges beyond technical demands. At the micro level (individual teachers), teachers' beliefs about learning shape their readiness to use technology for TPD, while their attitudes toward technology consistently influence EdTech adoption for TPD. At the meso level (schools and teacher colleges), institutional culture significantly influences how technology is adapted and implemented, with leadership shaping this culture. At the macro level (district or national), the collection and effective use of data from micro and meso levels are critical for sustaining program success. Successful implementation depends on the coordinated interplay of factors across all these levels to ensure a coherent system (Hennessy et al., 2022). This framework guided our analysis by linking each research question to specific system levels. RQ1 focused on micro-level teacher factors such as ICT skills, beliefs, and practices; RQ2 examined meso-level conditions such as school leadership, CoL facilitation, and access to support; and RQ3 explored macro-level influences related to policy and scalability. Cross-cutting elements such as infrastructure, connectivity, and access to technology were considered across all levels.

We hypothesised that structured technology-supported TPD through MEWAKA enhances teacher engagement by enabling flexible, collaborative, and relevant learning. Greater engagement encourages peer exchange and experimentation with new strategies, improving classroom practice. MEWAKA aims to support this through digital CoL modules and peer discussions that strengthen pedagogical application.

Figure 2. *Technology-mediated TPD ecosystem factors* (Source: Hennessy et al., 2022)

The role of emerging technologies in addressing TPD challenges

Emerging technologies hold transformative potential to overcome the barriers that hinder effective implementation of TPD in rural contexts. Technology has been found to bridge digital divides, enabling teachers to access TPD without the need for costly travel to TPD workshops conducted outside school premises (Mtebe & Raisamo, 2014). Mobile phones and tablets have been observed to afford teachers peer collaboration opportunities that are unrealistic—and thus typically missing in traditional TPD (UNESCO, 2018). Such technologies can be deployed in addressing infrastructural limitations by leveraging offline capabilities to ensure accessibility of learning materials for teachers in resource-constrained contexts (UNESCO, 2018).

Equally substantial is that technology has the potential to enhance the effectiveness, equity, and sustainability of TPD programs when designed and implemented with equity accommodations, such as screen readers,

font scaling, captions, and ergonomic devices, in mind (Trucano, 2016). It affords teachers opportunities to undergo personalized learning experiences, allowing them to focus on essential areas where they need the most support (Guskey, 2002). Hennessy et al. (2022) found that technology in TPD can support teacher self- and peer reflection, enhance subject knowledge and pedagogy, and foster flexible professional learning environments. They argue that technology revolutionises TPD, making it more impactful in strengthening teacher capacity. With such innovations in practice, Tanzania can build a resilient education system that empowers teachers to engage in effective TPD (World Bank, 2020). Building on this potential, our study tested key mechanisms to translate innovation into practice, such as offline access and the use of low-cost technologies, including Raspberry Pi devices and zero-rated TPD content.

Methodology

Research context

Our design-based implementation research (DBIR) study, undertaken jointly by members of government, Aga Khan University, and the [EdTech Hub](#) consortium team, followed MEWAKA implementation in 20 rural primary schools in four regions of Tanzania (Lindi, Dodoma, Mwanza and Iringa) for three years, from March 2022 through September 2025 in two phases of DBIR implementation (Figure 1). The first phase (March 2022–November 2023) examined the availability and use of technology to support TPD across eight schools in Lindi to lay the foundation for iterative design adjustments across three cycles. Cycle 0 piloted peer facilitator (PF) manuals and training to prepare schools for weekly CoLs (Koomar et al., 2024). Cycle 1 tested CoLs with varied technologies, including tablets and Raspberry Pi to identify implementation challenges (Koomar et al., 2024). Cycle 2 incorporated tablets, distributed PDF CoL modules, and refined data collection to track device usage, CoL frequency, teacher motivation, and female teacher participation (Chachage et al., 2024). These adjustments aimed to test the feasibility of different configurations for effective TPD to inform scalable, context-appropriate solutions. TIE refined LMS modules each cycle/round, while researchers led testing and iterative improvements of innovations, with the Ministry retaining content authority.

The second phase (October 2023 to September 2025) assessed equitable access and use of the TIE LMS to support TPD in 12 schools in four regions. In this phase, one school received a Raspberry Pi to access the LMS and

CoL modules, while four schools were provided with internet vouchers to access the LMS and its modules. The objectives were to examine challenges and opportunities for equitable technology-supported TPD in rural schools and to identify implications for scaling TPD more equitably in LMICs.

The research questions informing the analysis presented in this paper were:

- RQ1: How do teachers in rural Tanzania use technology within MEWAKA for professional development?
- RQ2: What challenges do teachers and facilitators face in utilizing technology for MEWAKA in rural Tanzania?
- RQ3: What are the opportunities for scaling technology-enabled MEWAKA in rural contexts?

Figure 1. Phased DBIR of MEWAKA implementation

Design

The findings presented in this article are drawn from a study that explored the effectiveness and long-term sustainability of the MEWAKA technology-supported, decentralised, school-based TPD model in enhancing learning outcomes in rural primary schools in Tanzania (Chachage et al., 2024; Koomar et al., 2024). The research aimed to test and iteratively improve the national MEWAKA model through DBIR, an “emerging approach to relating research and practice that is collaborative, iterative, and grounded in systematic inquiry” (University of Colorado School of Education, n.d.). The DBIR approach enabled researchers to collaborate with implementers in continuously refining the MEWAKA

model and its implementation, while also addressing initial challenges during the rollout of the initiative (Adam et al., under review).

DBIR is characterized by four key elements: a focus on enduring problems of practice viewed from the perspectives of multiple stakeholders; a commitment to iterative and collaborative design processes; an emphasis on generating theory related to both classroom learning and implementation through systematic inquiry; and a dedication to building capacity for sustaining systemic change (Penuel et al., 2011). It aims to develop theory and knowledge through a cyclical deductive-inductive process that allows for the boundaries of original ideas to be tested. In this study, co-design, iterative trial and refinement of new practices drew on existing theory and evidence regarding technology-supported TPD, in conjunction with learning from the practical context, including key stakeholders' needs.

The macro-, meso-, and micro-level factors in technology-mediated TPD (Figure 2) by Hennessy et al. (2022) served as an analytical framework for examining ecosystem influences, including teachers' technology use and practices, existing possibilities, and experienced technology use challenges at each level.

DBIR Evidence Box

- **Problem co-definition:** Limited access to structured, technology-supported TPD was jointly identified by teachers, school leaders, government stakeholders, and the DBIR team during initial consultations in early 2022.
- **Design cycles and evidence:** Over two months, the team conducted fortnightly school visits to observe classrooms and CoLs, followed by end-of-cycle focus groups and interviews aligned with cycle priorities. Findings were analysed to generate recommendations and evidence for the broader LMIC TPD knowledge base.
- **Theory adjustments:** Initial assumptions that digital access alone would enhance teacher engagement were refined to highlight the need for peer interaction and structured CoL time.
- **Capacity-building outcomes:** The process supported institutionalisation of evidence through stakeholder workshops, policy briefs, and integration of changes into the broader MEWAKA intervention.

Sample, data collection and analysis

Phase 1 of the DBIR, conducted from March 2022 to December 2023, involved two 4-month cycles, each aligned with a school calendar year, in eight primary schools in Lindi region. Each cycle included fortnightly CoL sessions spanning 2–3 months and end-of-cycle semi-structured focus

group discussions (FDGs), and key informant interviews and surveys. In Phase 2 (October 2023 to September 2025), two rounds of school-level data collection were conducted in 12 rural primary schools, including one TRC, in Lindi, Mwanza, Dodoma and Iringa, near the start and end of the 2024 school year. In this phase, we observed CoL sessions and classroom lessons, administered teacher surveys, and held semi-structured FDGs and interviewed teachers, school leaders, and education officers at ward, district, regional, and national levels. Phase 2 interviews and FDGs included participatory activities such as card sorts and small-group brainstorming. Regions were selected to reflect diverse contexts: Iringa and Dodoma with large donor-supported TPD initiatives, Lindi with a smaller foundation-led initiative, and Mwanza without major donor programs. Within these regions, the study took place in Kondoa (Dodoma), Iringa Rural (Iringa), Misungwi (Mwanza), and Mtama (Lindi), chosen for their predominantly rural characteristics based on government classifications and distance from urban centres. Three schools per region were selected within the same district based on the presence of teachers with disabilities and differing levels of technology access and connectivity. All available teachers participated, with overlapping samples across cycles/rounds. Teachers with disabilities were included to ensure adequate representation, not for comparative analysis; disability was considered part of participants' broader equity profile. Because the study drew on different school samples in each phase, the observed Phase 1–Phase 2 differences likely reflect regional variation rather than to changes over time.

Ethical approval and necessary permissions were granted by the national research ethics review board (Commission for Science and Technology) and local government authorities. Informed consent was obtained from all participants. Identifying information was removed, and data was stored securely on password-protected systems. To minimise courtesy bias, we used anonymous surveys, neutral questioning, confidentiality assurances, and avoided revealing researchers' titles. Assistant researchers received a week of training on ethical data-collection procedures. Potential risks were minimized through careful facilitation and protection of participant privacy. We also reduced the risk of overrepresenting digitally confident teachers by using multiple methods to capture wider perspectives. Research tools were piloted during the baseline phase and were iteratively refined, especially following the end-of-cycle/round evaluations. The instruments have been openly published in both [English](#) and [Swahili](#).

Data from surveys and CoL observations were gathered using mWater, an offline data collection application. The surveys were configured to require responses; in the rare cases that responses were missing for a CoL

observation, the video recording of the CoL was used to fill in the missing data. Inter-rater reliability training for rating items on the observation protocols was conducted in each phase of the study, and we supported consistency through joint reviews and regular alignment discussions. Data was exported, cleaned, and analyzed using descriptive statistics (e.g., frequencies, means) to identify patterns and trends. FDG and interview data were transcribed and thematically coded using Atlas.ti. The coding for Cycle 1 was initially undertaken by assistant researchers; however, all transcripts were subsequently re-coded by three senior researchers to ensure consistency and analytical rigor. For Cycle 2 and both rounds of Phase 2, the same three senior researchers conducted the coding process to ensure inter-rater reliability. Discrepancies in coding were discussed collectively and resolved through consensus. The codebook was developed using a combination of deductive and inductive approaches. Deductive codes were informed by the study's RQs and the ecosystem model, resulting in predefined categories such as barriers, enablers, and financial resources, as well as levels of operation including teacher-level, school-level, ward-level, and district-level factors. Inductive codes were added iteratively as recurring themes and patterns emerged from the data. For example, a sub-code for "cost of internet" was introduced under the broader code "insufficient funds" after it appeared frequently across interviews. Data were also cross-coded to reflect multiple dimensions; for instance, a teacher reporting the cost of internet as a barrier would be coded simultaneously as "teacher-level," "barrier," and "cost of internet."

Table 1. *Data sources*

Instrument	Phase 1		Phase 2	
	Cycle 1 Sample (4 schools)	Cycle 2 Sample (8 schools)	Round 1 Sample (12 schools)	Round 2 Sample (12 schools)
CoL meeting observations	15	40	12	12
Teacher survey	25 teachers	52 teachers	125 teachers	N/A
Teacher focus groups	3	7	11	11
School MEWAKA leadership team focus groups	4	8	11	11
Education officer interviews	8	5	21	17

Researchers analysed the data to develop government recommendations for strengthening TPD implementation and to contribute to the broader evidence base in LMICs. After each cycle and phase, we held a one-day

workshop with national implementation leaders to prioritise key recommendations (Koomar et al., 2024). We subsequently shared the findings and recommendations with teachers and leaders at all administrative levels for validation. Their insights guided iterative refinements to the MEWAKA plan and helped identify priorities for the next data-collection round.

Findings

Technology use for TPD

In Phase 1, teachers and Ward Education Officers (WEOs) reported using phones and tablets to access the LMS and share resources and strategies with other teachers via social media. Teachers reported using personal phones and government-issued tablets regularly, often daily, for TPD. They also noted using other personal devices for professional learning. Although teachers did not often bring their technological devices to CoL sessions, some teachers used them to read materials before or after sessions. Moreover, 86.5% (45 out of 52 teachers) reported that PFs and teachers used their own mobile data credit to access materials in their own time and/or in CoL sessions. As one teacher said,

“In our CoL sessions, many of us use our own internet bundles to access materials. I often see peer facilitators preparing the session sometimes using their own phones just to smoothly run the session”

In Phase 2 Round 1, 88% (110 out of 125 teachers) reported using various technological devices for TPD, although usage patterns varied across schools. Smartphones were the most commonly used, reported in 5 schools (42%), followed by tablets in 4 schools (33%) and laptops in 3 schools (25%). The most popular use of the basic mobile phone by 46.4% (57 teachers) was giving and receiving feedback to peer teachers for their professional development. One school used a desktop computer specifically for a CoL session aimed at teaching teachers how to use Microsoft Word. However, we found limited awareness and underutilisation of digital CoL modules hosted on the LMS. Despite the availability of 12 new, specially designed modules, CoL observations conducted in March 2024 showed that only 2 out of 12 schools used the modules. In a follow-up survey in May 2024, head teachers reported slightly different levels of use of the modules by teachers: 7 out of 12 schools (58.3%) did not use them at all, 4 (33.3%) seldom used them, and only 1 school reported using them regularly. Teacher survey data further highlight this issue, with 36% (45 out of 125 teachers) reporting accessing the LMS weekly or more, while 35.2%

(44 teachers) accessed it rarely (i.e., once or twice a year), and 12% (15 teachers) had never accessed the LMS. Yet, a regional comparison showed that 70.4% (88 teachers) in Dodoma accessed the LMS rarely or never, in comparison to 30.4% (38 teachers) in Iringa. Teachers in two schools reported using the LMS modules, and one made use of the PF Manual during CoL sessions.

The use of technology in CoL sessions was lower in Round 2, as no basic phones, smartphones, tablets, or laptops were used in any of the observed CoLs, and only one CoL used desktop computers. LMS-hosted resources such as the CoL module and the PF manual were absent, except for one CoL (8%) that used a soft copy (downloaded) PDF CoL module. This was one of the schools that received internet vouchers to access the LMS and modules. In the school that had received a Raspberry Pi and three of the four schools that received internet vouchers, digital tools were not used during observed CoL sessions, though a PF from the school with a Raspberry Pi mentioned using the modules for CoL preparation. As one PF expressed,

“I use the modules on the Raspberry Pi to prepare before the meetings so I can better guide the group during the CoL session. It helps me feel more prepared, even if we don’t use the device during the sessions”

Teacher and stakeholder perspectives on technology use for TPD

In Phase 1, teachers perceived several benefits of using technology for TPD, including quick and convenient access to learning materials and enhanced engagement. In Phase 2, teachers at 9 out of 11 schools shared positive views on the use of technology for TPD. 84.8% (106 out of 125 teachers) affirmed that technology does support their personal development “a lot,” citing improvements in knowledge and ability to search for learning materials and resources. They underscored the value of online platforms in expanding their content knowledge beyond what is available locally, viewing it as a resource for both personal growth and improved instructional practice, as one teacher explained:

“I rely on my phone to Google meanings and access learning videos. MEWAKA has supported me in tackling difficult challenges, particularly with syllabus interpretation.”

In addition, teachers considered technology highly useful for communication and collaboration. In schools visited, teachers had

established WhatsApp groups to support ongoing dialogue, share TPD resources, and exchange teaching materials. For them, these platforms allowed for information-sharing and peer learning. Teachers valued these digital spaces for maintaining professional connections and building a supportive learning community. WEOs echoed this sentiment, as one explained,

“Technology lets teachers share information from one place to another. Before, they’d have to visit another school to see what their colleagues were doing, but now they can share ideas and resources without even leaving their own school.”

Operational challenges in technology use for TPD

Lack of essential technological devices for TPD

Teachers reported a lack of essential technological devices such as tablets, basic mobile phones, smartphones, laptops, and televisions to support their professional learning. Data show that a significant proportion of teachers lack essential technology, with 60.8% (76 out of 125 teachers) having no access to laptops and 39.2% (49 teachers) missing other devices such as TVs or desktop computers limiting their access to CoL modules and other TPD resources. 11.2% (14 teachers) indicated they did not own a tablet, as they had been employed after the initial distribution of government census tablets in 2022 (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Access to technology devices among teachers

Lack of functioning software or accommodations to support teachers with disabilities

In the Phase 1 survey, 80.8% (42 out of 52 teachers) who self-identified as having disabilities, either through a doctor's diagnosis or functional limitations, reported that the technology available to them was highly suitable for their specific needs, including teachers with visual and mobility impairments. However, others reported a lack of any functioning software or accommodations on technological devices to support teachers with disabilities. As a result, they depended on their peers to navigate devices and read materials aloud. They further reported reduced motivation in using technology because they "can't see anything." We provide a more detailed discussion of this challenge for teachers with disabilities in our separate paper (Hennessy et al., under review).

Limited connectivity, unreliable electricity, and the cost of internet data

Teachers reported limited connectivity, unreliable electricity, and the high cost of internet data to pose significant challenges to the effective use of technology for TPD across schools in both phases. They considered these challenges as hindering their access to the LMS and its modules, limiting their participation in TPD activities. Alternatively, teachers noted relying on their personal mobile data to access TPD materials since some schools had no reliable network. Teachers from 4 of the 12 Phase 2 schools specifically cited internet costs as a barrier to accessing LMS and CoL modules, as one member of the TCPD team noted:

"Teachers are ready and motivated for CoL[s] but the challenge is that there is no power, no network for them to explore online materials until they travel to town, which is expensive."

However, in schools that were provided with RPi, teachers considered the devices to be valuable in providing access to CoL modules.

Limited digital literacy and confidence in using technology

Across DBIR phases, teachers identified limited digital literacy as a significant challenge, with female teachers disproportionately affected. They noted that such a situation is compounded by factors such as limited ICT training (male teachers more often selected for ICT training) and inadequate access to resources, thereby hampering their ability to use tablets or computers to engage in TPD activities. LGA officers echoed teachers' sentiment, noting that limited digital skills pose a significant challenge to teachers, as one explained:

“Not every teacher was conversant with the access to the LMS. It took me a couple of minutes to guide them. Three teachers out of nine were able to reach the LMS site successfully.”

Lower women’s engagement in technology use was reported by teachers of both sexes in all 12 Phase 2 schools, attributed to societal factors such as prioritization of household spending priorities over TPD-related costs, lower interest or motivation in technology, lower confidence in using technology, influence of traditional/patriarchal beliefs, and greater personal device ownership among men. To address these issues, teachers reported relying on peers for technological support.

Policy-related challenges in technology use for TPD

Lack of guidelines on maintenance and replacement of tablets

Teachers reported a policy gap regarding the maintenance and replacement of government-issued tablets. Across DBIR phases, they reported a lack of clear guidelines for addressing malfunctions and replacements, becoming uncertain about where to seek support when their tablets became nonfunctional. This lack of policy raised concerns around responsibility—whether the responsibility for tablet maintenance and replacement lies with the school, ward, district, or central government. One teacher explained,

“Some of our tablets aren’t working, and we don’t know where to take them to get them fixed. There’s no clear guidance on who is responsible, so we’re left unsure what to do.”

Financial constraints

TCPD teams and WEOs cited limited budgets as a key challenge in implementing technology-supported MEWAKA, viewing it as a policy gap. Schools. They reported the absence of dedicated funds for sustaining technology-supported CoL sessions was a major barrier. Even though they acknowledged the presence of a policy around capitation grants, they considered it insufficient to support MEWAKA. They further reported that the policy lacks provisions for budget allocation to procure tablets for newly recruited teachers, replace non-functional tablets, or subsidize internet bundles, all of which are key enablers for accessing LMS modules. One WEO noted,

“We have new teachers who need tablets, and others who can’t afford internet bundles, but we don’t have enough resources for that.”

Also, as WEOs we are expected to visit schools to observe CoLs, we need funds for buying fuel which adds to the challenge.”

Possibilities for scaling TPD using technology

Broad reach of mobile technology in Tanzania

The widespread availability of mobile technology in Tanzania, including in rural areas, offers strong potential for scaling technology-supported TPD. According to the Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority, there were approximately 20.5 million smartphones in the country by June 2024, with the highest ownership among adults aged 20–34, aligning with earlier estimates indicating that mobile penetration in Tanzania is close to 80% (Tanzania Communications Regulatory Authority, 2024), making mobile devices one of the most accessible platforms for reaching teachers across Tanzania. Despite this significant mobile reach, we acknowledge that the constraints reported in rural schools underscore a continuing digital divide.

WhatsApp has emerged as a preferred communication and learning tool among teachers, reporting using it to share learning materials, ask pedagogical questions, discuss classroom practices, and coordinate CoL sessions. In some districts, WhatsApp groups connected hundreds of teachers, providing an informal yet effective space for peer support. This demonstrates the potential of leveraging mobile platforms to extend the reach of TPD programs. With appropriate support, including curated content, moderation, and structured facilitation, WhatsApp can serve as a bridge between high mobile phone use and LMS adoption, offering a cost-effective, scalable, and sustainable model for TPD, particularly in rural contexts within LMICs.

Centralized TPD content

The TIE LMS, available as a mobile phone app, provides a centralized platform for delivering CoL modules, enabling scalable and streamlined access to TPD content. It holds significant promise for reaching teachers in rural areas at a minimal cost per user (teacher). The LMS, with centralized content delivery, has the potential to ensure consistency in the quality of TPD materials and facilitate timely updates to the content. Although scaling this initiative is investment-intensive in terms of digital infrastructure and reliable connectivity, it offers the potential for promoting equitable access to learning resources and supporting TPD in LMICs, as well as providing a powerful TPD monitoring and evaluation tool through the LMS analytics dashboard and the potential for teacher feedback mechanisms.

Increased teacher collaboration and confidence

Observations from both teachers and TCPD teams across schools surveyed confirm that technology-supported TPD contributes to improved teacher collaboration and confidence. For example, in three out of four schools in Phase 1 Cycle 1, there was a marked increase in these attributes among teachers. The reported increase in teacher collaboration and confidence, driven by accessible technologies such as WhatsApp, underscores a significant opportunity for scaling TPD via digital platforms in LMICs.

Increased teacher CoL participation and motivation

Survey findings from Phase 1, Cycle 2 indicate that 96.2% (50 out of 52 teachers) regularly attended weekly CoL sessions at their schools, with 65% (34 out of 52 teachers) also participating in monthly sessions at TRCs. Attendance in CoLs ranged from 63% to 100%, further demonstrating teachers' commitment to collaborative learning. Importantly, 90% (47 out of 52 teachers) described their motivation to participate in CoL sessions as "a lot," and over 90% (n=47) expressed enjoyment for the CoL activities. The reported increased motivation for CoL activities highlights a fertile ground for expanding scalable, technology-supported TPD that enhances continuous teacher learning. Thus, leveraging technology platforms to deliver and support CoL sessions can capitalize on this existing motivation to enable wider reach and more flexible access to TPD in LMICs.

Emerging opportunities for TPD enabled by technology

Researchers tested targeted innovations aimed at addressing the reported barriers and strengthening TPD. The innovations revealed emerging opportunities for enhancing the reach and effectiveness of technology-enabled TPD in rural contexts.

Supporting schools with offline LMS

The use of offline resources through Raspberry Pi devices presents a promising and cost-effective approach to delivering pre-loaded CoL modules in rural schools. In one school provided with the device, the PF noted that it was more efficient for accessing CoL modules compared to internet-dependent devices, primarily due to unreliable connectivity. No technical challenges were reported in the school using the device since its installment in September 2024. This suggests that, when introduced with adequate initial technical support, the device can be a practical offline LMS solution for addressing infrastructural barriers and promoting equitable access to TPD in rural schools (Woodward et al., 2022). Our sample is

relatively small; however, Raspberry Pis have demonstrated successful large-scale application in Zambia for similar TPD purposes (The Open University, 2025).

Providing schools with internet data

Providing schools with internet bundles was tested during the DBIR implementation and showed promising results. Teachers reported improved access to digital CoL modules and greater ability to collaborate with peers within their schools and nearby. This intervention demonstrated how reliable and affordable connectivity can enhance both access to TPD content and engagement within teacher networks. Rwanda launched a similar initiative, providing internet access to rural schools for learning purposes (Martin, 2020). Thus, leveraging this innovation can help expand TPD opportunities to rural schools.

Zero-rating LMS content

Partnerships with mobile network providers to zero-rate LMS content represent a promising strategy to ensure teachers have reliable access to CoL digital modules. Teachers noted that this mechanism has the potential of reducing financial barriers, thereby enhancing equitable TPD. As such, it holds the potential to expand equitable access to TPD and foster sustained teacher growth. Implementation of this initiative has not yet been fully realized in Tanzania, as only one telecom company, Vodacom Tanzania, has partnered with the government to zero-rate TPD content for teachers subscribed to its network (The Guardian, 2025). In other LMICs, a similar initiative has been implemented; for instance, the Kenya government partnered with Safaricom and Airtel to zero-rate access to online teacher learning materials to expand TPD opportunities.

Offering multiple access pathways to increase TPD accessibility

Providing multiple access options for digital CoL modules proved essential for increasing accessibility among teachers in rural schools. Teachers reported that accessing modules in downloadable format helped them to access the TPD content offline. This offline availability complemented digital delivery methods and overcame infrastructural barriers but also guaranteed that all schools, regardless of internet access, could have access to TPD resources. These findings highlight the value of integrating both low-tech and no-tech solutions alongside digital tools to create inclusive, sustainable TPD in rural areas. Zambia has implemented a similar initiative at scale by loading TPD materials onto offline tablets, which teachers can use directly in their schools (Tegha et al., 2021).

Strengthening peer technology support

Teachers in rural areas reported a strong willingness to support each other in overcoming challenges related to technology use, indicating a valuable opportunity to enhance peer support systems. Through developing the digital literacy of select teachers to serve as technology “champions,” schools could foster a sustainable model for ongoing technical assistance. As a case in point, primary teachers with advanced digital skills reported supporting their peers with limited experience, while those with internet bundles and smartphones shared connectivity resources to improve access. Such local initiatives demonstrate the potential of peer-driven technology support to enhance TPD in resource-constrained settings. Some LMICs, including Uganda, have leveraged this opportunity by engaging in peer-to-peer training to support professional learning (Mugisha et al., 2023).

Discussion

Findings of our DBIR offer convergent evidence that the MEWAKA model holds considerable promise for transforming TPD and improving teaching. However, its scalability depends significantly on how technological, infrastructural, financial, and policy-related barriers are addressed by education authorities in Tanzania, which may offer a useful case for other LMICs to learn from.

Technology as a catalyst for teacher professional growth

Our research found that teachers in rural schools are gradually engaging with technology, particularly WhatsApp for collaborative learning and sharing resources available within their spheres of control. This is consistent with existing literature that increasingly emphasizes the role of mobile technology in supporting TPD in low-resource settings (Hennessy et al., 2022; Trucano, 2016). It is increasingly considered useful in supporting a shift from traditional professional practice to a more collaborative, peer-supported approach. Despite challenges in accessing digital CoL modules, the approach has been reported to encourage teachers to engage in collaborations and peer support. These findings align with Seboka et al. (2025), who reported the positive impact of technology-supported TPD on teaching practices and student achievement.

Further, teachers are accessing TPD materials via the LMS alongside online digital resources that are otherwise rarely accessible. Although our sample is limited to a few schools, this situation illustrates a context-related blended model of TPD for teachers in rural contexts, observed to cater for the varying teacher needs but also allowed for increased flexibility among teachers in accessing resources for TPD (West & Vosloo, 2013; Seboka et al., 2025). Moreover, the model is suited to respond to technological challenges facing schools in LMICs, which are well-documented in prior research on the integration of technology in TPD (Hennessy et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2016).

Barriers to scalability and equity

Despite the innovations tested in our work, the study highlights critical constraints that hamper the full implementation and effectiveness of MEWAKA in rural schools. The first barrier is technological: teachers lack technological devices for TPD. Even among those with access to digital devices, unreliable electricity and poor internet connectivity limit consistent engagement with digital CoL modules to support CoL sessions. These findings align with previous research highlighting the digital divide between urban and rural education systems in LMICs (Hennessy et al., 2022). The high cost of internet data for rural teachers creates both a financial burden and an access gap, reinforcing inequalities linked to geography and socioeconomic status. Similar concerns have emerged in studies of mobile learning in rural contexts, which caution against relying on technology for TPD without first addressing affordability and access (Haßler et al., 2016).

Digital literacy emerged as a major barrier to teachers' use of technology for TPD. Many reported requiring peer support for basic tasks, a challenge known to hinder engagement with LMS modules. The link between digital confidence and engagement supports the MEWAKA framework, which suggests that greater digital literacy enhances preparedness and participation in CoL activities. The need for digital literacy support for teachers is consistent with broader findings in the literature on technology for TPD in LMICs, which calls for implementing context-relevant, capacity-building programs to empower teachers to use technology for TPD (Hennessy et al., 2022; UNESCO, 2018).

Particularly concerning are the challenges teachers with disabilities face in accessing and using technology to fully engage with TPD content. The study shows they encounter multiple intersecting barriers, including

inaccessible software and hardware, lack of assistive technologies to support their professional learning, and a lack of policy frameworks that support inclusive TPD. These findings echo global concerns about the marginalization of persons with disabilities in digital learning environments (World Bank, 2020; UNICEF, 2019) and calls for the development of procurement standards for assistive devices to ensure accessible devices are included in TPD.

These barriers explain the gap we observed between teachers' strong enthusiasm for digital tools and their relatively limited actual use, showing that positive attitudes alone cannot overcome structural constraints. Acknowledging these interconnected constraints provides a basis for the next section, which introduces opportunities for scaling TPD.

Opportunities for scaling and sustainability

The study identifies several opportunities to enhance the scalability, sustainability, and inclusivity of technology-supported TPD (Table 2). The first opportunity is the use of offline, low-cost technologies, including Raspberry Pi devices, to host pre-loaded digital CoL modules without requiring constant internet access and advanced digital literacy in its management. The devices, including accessible interfaces, screen readers, audio-visual content, and alternative input methods can help teachers with disabilities access digital CoL modules. The second is zero-rating TPD content and providing it in multiple formats (text, audio, video, captions) with full compatibility for assistive technologies, to allow teachers to reliably access TPD materials.

One more opportunity is strengthening school-level peer support systems. The emergence of informal digital learning networks, particularly through WhatsApp, suggests that teacher collaboration can be leveraged for wider capacity building. Institutionalizing these networks can help create a sustainable school-level support structure for ongoing digital skills development among teachers in rural contexts. Teacher colleagues, along with a few trained to offer-disability-inclusive digital support, can serve as first-line support for their peers within their schools to reduce over-reliance on external technical experts but also enhance local ownership (Leu et al., 2015). These innovations have been successfully piloted in other LMICs and have offered a promising pathway for scaling technology-supported TPD to areas with minimal technological infrastructure (Hennessy et al., 2022).

Table 2. *Cost-Impact grid*

Opportunity	Cost	Impact	Actor
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Use of offline and low-cost technologies, such as Raspberry Pi devices	Low	High	Ministry of Education
Zero-rating TPD content	Low	High	Tanzania Institute of Education
Strengthening school-level peer support systems	Low	High	Schools and local government authorities

This synthesis links key barriers for technology use for TPD with opportunities such as offline low-cost tools, zero-rated TPD content, and stronger peer support. In line with the MEWAKA framework, the findings highlight digital confidence, accessible infrastructure, and collaboration as core mechanisms. They show that scalable, equitable technology policy requires reducing structural barriers while strengthening support systems that enable all teachers to participate meaningfully.

Implications for policy and practice

The findings from our study offer several implications for policy and practice aimed at enhancing the scalability of technology-supported TPD in LMICs. First, the ministry of education and all mobile network providers should zero-rate TPD content to ensure that at least 90% of teachers, including those with disabilities, can access learning materials without incurring data costs. Second, the ministry of education and TIE should conduct a systematic evaluation of government-issued tablets across diverse school contexts, tracking metrics including device functionality, frequency of use, and teacher satisfaction to inform future deployment and support strategies for equitable distribution, training, and support. Third, LGAs should establish an ICT Champion role in each school (or wards/districts), allocating basic training and time for the role, with at least 80% of teachers receiving peer-led technology support for TPD. These champions, trained to offer disability-inclusive support, can help colleagues with disabilities use digital tools and platforms for TPD. This cost-effective model, successful in other settings, can strengthen local ownership and digital literacy within schools, especially in rural areas. Fourth, TIE must provide offline versions of the LMS to all rural schools to ensure that at least 90% of teachers in these schools can access TPD content, regardless of geographical location and infrastructural constraints. Likewise, TIE must report 3–5 key LMS metrics, including active users, module completion, CoL attendance, accessibility fulfilment, and device uptime, on a quarterly basis, with the goal of tracking engagement and informing strategies to ensure scalable and equitable TPD. These measures are essential for creating a more equitable and sustainable TPD ecosystem.

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